

Spectrophotometric method for the determination of isoniazid

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Abstract : The observation that carbon disulphide transforms isoniazid in methanol medium into isonicotinylidithiocarbazic acid and the latter reacts with uranyl acetate in the same medium rapidly and quantitatively to form soluble bright yellow uranyl isonicotinylidithiocarbazate complex, has been made the basis of a simple, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of isoniazid. The measurements are made at 410 nm.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, isoniazide.

Isoniazid (isonicotinic acid hydrazide, (1), is a remarkably effective drug and is now considered one of the primary drugs for chemotherapy of tuberculosis¹. The analysis of this drug² like other drugs for their active ingredient contents is an important part of the drug analysis. The existing method (macro)³ lacks the simplicity, rapidity and sensitivity, commonly required in routine analysis of a drug. The proposed method is based on the observations that : (i) in methanol medium, carbon disulphide transforms isoniazid into isonicotinylidithiocarbazic acid (INDtczH) (2), and (ii) in the same medium, 2 reacts with uranyl acetate smoothly, rapidly and quantitatively forming soluble bright yellow uranyl isonicotinylidithiocarbazate complex, plausibly (3), show-

ing λ_{max} at 410 nm. The colour which develops immediately on adding the reagent to 2, is stable for atleast 2.5 h.

The method just consists in adding a drop of carbon disulphide to methanolic solution of isoniazid, followed by the addition of uranyl acetate (in methanol). The absorbance of the bright yellow solution thus obtained is

measured at 410 nm and the results calculated on the basis of calibration graph (between concentration and absorbance) constructed from pure sample of isoniazid.

Experimental

Chemicals : Carbon disulphide (A.R., Merck) and methanol (A.R., Merck) were used as such. Isoniazid (a drug based on isonicotinic acid) was procured from local market. Uranyl acetate dihydrate-UO₂(OAc)₂·2H₂O (American Praparate) : its standard solution was prepared in methanol. Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer (Spectronic 20D), with 1 cm matched glass cells, was used for all absorption measurements.

Procedures : Preparation of calibration graph : Aliquots of solution in methanol of the pure drug compound were mixed with carbon disulphide (1 drop; ~50 μ l) and uranyl acetate dihydrate (1 ml, 0.001 M in methanol) and the volume made upto 5 ml with methanol. The absorbance of the bright yellow solution was measured at 410 nm and a calibration curve was prepared as usual. The Beer's law is followed upto 50 μ g/ml of isoniazid.

Drug analysis : A known number of tablets of the drug were crushed and a single large sample weighed. It was shaken with methanol and filtered. The residue, (if any) was washed 2-3 times with the same solvent and the filtrate along with washings diluted to known volume with methanol. Aliquots of this solution were processed for colorimetric analysis in the manner as given above for the pure compound.

Results and discussion

The molar absorptivity of the yellow uranyl

isonicotinyldithiocarbamate complex, (3), is $1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ L}^{-1}$ (on the basis of isoniazid content); as little as 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of the isoniazid can be analysed by the method. The most attractive features of this colorimetric method are the instantaneous development of the colour and its sufficient stability and clear stoichiometry. It has further been established by carrying out the photometric titrations of isonicotinyldithiocarbamic acid (formed from isoniazid through reaction with carbon disulphide in methanol) with the reagent, which are marked by a well-defined intersection at drug to reagent molar ratio of 2 : 1. Further support to the formation of (3) is provided by the fact that uranyl salts do form such type of complexes with dithiocarbamates⁴.

The results of analysis indicate that isoniazid in the range 4–50 μg could be determined with maximum relative standard deviation of 0.8%. When applied to the

assay of commercial drugs (INH-100, INH-300. Isokin. Solonex and Isoniazid), the recoveries were in the range of 99.5–99.9% of the nominal content with RSD's in the range 0.55–0.8%. The results have been compared with the IP method³ whereby the recoveries fall in the range 98.5–99.8% with RSD's in the range 0.66–0.85%.

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